

WIND OPERATED TRAVELING CHARGER

SHIVRAJ BIRAJDAR¹,
OMKAR KABBUR²,
SHITAL POTDAR³,
YOGESH MAHAMUNI⁴,
CHAKOLE M.M. ⁵

^{1,2,3,4}Student, Department of Mechanical Engineering, A.G.Patil Institute of Technology,

⁵Assistant Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, A.G. Patil Institute of Technology, Solapur.

ABSTRACT

This work is mainly based on the concept of wind mill to generate DC voltage/electricity and this generated power can be used for various purposes. By using this concept, we develop wind operated traveling charger. Smart phones are mostly used during traveling for various purposes like internet browsing/entertainment/social media. Mostly charging facility is not available during traveling. As Wind is adequate source of energy which is available at free of cost. The use of high velocity air flow through turbine for mechanically power generation.

When fan rotates by application of wind, wind energy is converted into mechanical energy and this mechanical energy is converted into electrical energy by using DC generator. This generated power supplied to IC 7805 which regulates and gives constant output of 5v. Generally, every ordinary mobile require 5v input supply to charge its battery. Female USB port is used as end effector, by using data cable we can connect it to our mobile and its battery.

KEYWORDS: Wind energy, traveling charger, renewable source of energy.